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Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

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Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning: FEMaLe

WP9. BEACON: dissemination, communication, and synergies.

D9.7 – Innovation and Intellectual Property management plan and reporting.

1. Introduction

The *Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning* (FEMaLe) project is at its final stage, and this report delves into the significant strides made in innovation, emphasising the continued effort to disseminate and leverage these findings effectively. WP9 continues to play a key role in driving our efforts forward, focusing on the dissemination, communication, and exploitation of results, ensuring that the project's impact is maximised through strategic public disclosure and intellectual and innovation property (IIP) management. This document outlines our latest advancements, aligning with the project's commitment to open and impactful scientific communication.

2. Strategies

The strategic approach in WP9 has been to ensure a robust management of intellectual and innovation property (IIP), a critical aspect in this international and collaborative project. Key objectives include:

Protection of Pre-Existing Knowledge:

Emphasising the importance of recognising and safeguarding each partner's contributions and associated IIP rights.

Protection and Utilisation of Project-Acquired Knowledge:

Encouraging timely dissemination of project results and determining the ownership, use rights, and terms of agreement.

Effective Collaboration with Partners:

Leveraging the expertise of partners in similar fields and outlining clear IIP collaboration terms for efficient knowledge exchange.

The Consortium Agreement (CA), aligned with international standards of IIP protection, provides the legal framework for these strategies, with ongoing support to address essential points.

3. Actions

Our action plan focuses on two fronts: *innovation* and its *protection*. This not only showcases the project's technological excellence but also secures the IIP rights associated with these products.

4. Lucy App: Next Step

Over the years, the *Lucy App* has been developed to the point where the basic features work well. The app successfully fulfills the unique task of educating and warning its users if, based on the reported symptoms, it might be worth visiting a gynecologist so that any existing diseases (such as endometriosis, for example) can be diagnosed in time.

This is evidenced by the excellent evaluation of the app, the number of active users, which is now close to 20,000, as well as the hundreds of grateful letters and reviews in the app stores, in which users report that the information and messages provided by the app helped them get timely help and improved their quality of life.

However, in order to operate Lucy in a stable manner despite the ever-increasing number of users, as well as to be able to further develop it with the functions desired by experts and users, it is necessary for the app to enter a new phase from the current completely non-profit model and to make its operation move to a financially self-sustaining business model.

On the one hand, this could help to spread its beneficial effect - which is already supported by research - to as many people as possible in Europe (or even the whole world), and on the other hand, it would allow us to implement the many plans and developments that we have in mind regarding the app.

The business direction we envisioned would be the implementation of a *freemium* model. As part of this, the currently available functions would still be available for free, but we would include a subscription option in the application, with which they could become Lucy Premium users, gaining access to new unique and useful functions. We plan to implement the following functions in the near future, if we manage to attract the appropriate capital for the development:

a. Prediction models based on Artificial Intelligence (High impact – High effort)

We would use technologies so that the application not only calculates with statically selected menstruation and ovulation data, but also continuously calculates the expected date of the next menstruation and ovulation based on the user's individual entries and symptoms, as well as the guidelines of AI models trained with our entire user base. This would greatly contribute to users being able to plan their everyday lives more easily and more accurately, and to get to know their own bodies, and it would also be of great help to couples struggling with conceiving problems, which are becoming increasingly problematic nowadays.

We have already prepared a proof of concept for the plans, which worked well, and the feasibility was ensured.

b. Integration of risk profiles completed during FEMaLe 2020, further development with AI technologies (High impact – High effort)

The current symptom monitoring module of the application has already tested well based on the data of the past years, but we could further develop it both on the basis of the big data research completed during the FEMaLe project and with trained AI models in order to help even more people get early diagnosis and care.

c. Mindfulness module native integration (MY-ENDO) (Mid impact – Mid effort)

The digital mindfulness program completed as part of the FEMaLe project's WP8 produced promising results, however, in order to make the most of it, it would be worthwhile to natively integrate the program into the mobile application. It should be much easier and more ergonomic to use than the current web user interface, thereby helping to achieve the highest possible user retention. At the same time, by handling the data in the context of Lucy, it is also possible to conduct the examination of participation in the mindfulness program and pain symptoms together, which can be an excellent tool for both the further validation of the program and its further development.

d. Pregnancy management module (Mid impact – Mid effort)

The application currently has the option of recording pregnancy, but there are still many open options in this topic. Both the implementation of helpful functions that follow the process of getting pregnant, as well as information and tools that can be used during pregnancy, could greatly help users who wish to have a child.

e. Application theming (Low impact – Low effort)

The current user interface of the application follows a uniquely imagined visual world, however, users could feel the application closer to themselves if they had the opportunity to change the illustrations, colors and themes.

In addition to the implementation of the above premium modules, it would also be important to allocate resources for the further development of the basic application in order to ensure the retention of the existing user base and to conquer new markets as quickly as possible:

a. E-mail/social app login

One of the most requested functions of the application is that users can be created by email or social app login. In the current concept, due to the preservation of anonymity, we do not use any personal data, even during the creation of users, but this means that if the users lose or forget their password, access to the stored data can potentially be terminated. We would change this by using the usual access methods (e-mail, social login) as in other apps, however, we would pay special attention to ensure that the uploaded data is still stored encrypted, we would solve data security by anonymizing it when used for research and analysis

b. Gamification

For users, it can greatly contribute to their engagement with the application if it is equipped with game-like elements. We would increase the engagement of our users by implementing unique avatars, illustrations, achievements, point systems and/or mini-games that reward regular activity.

c. Daily tips

The application could be a very good platform for providing advice to users with unique, personalized messages every day. For this, we would create a system in which thousands of advice, suggestions, and information are annotated according to the cases in which they are relevant, so it might be worth opening the app every day to get new useful information. This platform can also be a suitable basis for achieving sponsorship messages and monetization.

d. Integration of data from third parties

It would be a useful addition to the app both for users and during data mining if it were possible to import data recorded in other applications. Calendars (Google Calendar), health apps (Google Fit, Apple Health), sports apps, etc.

e. Formatted data export

Exports that can be downloaded in different formats would allow users to easily share some of their data from Lucy, thus promoting, for example, the accuracy and efficiency of private healthcare (integration with their internal systems already on the market).

f. In-depth training materials and articles

The deepening of the currently existing educational articles and the inclusion of additional materials and advice would greatly contribute to making health education even more prominent in the app. In addition to the analysis of entries, education is the other main leg of the process, which promotes early diagnosis of users and access to help.

The design, testing and development of the listed functions would require quite a lot of resources, however, with the transition to the freemium model, the application could quickly become self-sufficient, so growth could be ensured even without external sources of income.

5. Conclusions

The FEMaLe project has made remarkable progress in its mission to revolutionise the early detection and understanding of endometriosis right to the end. This final report underscores the significant innovative contributions made thus far, with emphasis on the *Lucy* App, reflecting our commitment to impactful research and effective IIP management. As we move beyond the project period, our focus remains on leveraging these outcomes to benefit the wider society and particularly those affected by endometriosis.